

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

СИСТЕМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСАМИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ

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ENTERPRISE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются вопросы системы управления финансами предприятия. Как известно, финансы предприятий являются основой как общерыночной, так и общегосударственной экономической системы. Эффективная система управления финансовыми ресурсами предприятия является основой высокой эффективности деятельности предприятия и дает возможность его дальнейшего развития и продвижения и укрепления позиций на рынке.

Abstract

The article deals with questions about enterprise financial management system. As it known, the finances of enterprises are the basis of both the general market and the nationwide economic system. An effective system for managing the financial resources of an enterprise is the basis for high performance in enterprises and provides an opportunity for its further development and promotion and strengthening of its position in the market.

Ключевые слова: финансы, система управления, предприятие, финансовый менеджмент.

Keywords: finance, management system, enterprise, financial management.

The main thing in Graham's theory is not forecasts, but discipline.

Benjamin Graham

Introduction.

Financial management of an enterprise is the work of a financial manager who plans, organizes and controls all company operations, analyzes changes in the structure and volume of funds of financial resources, and monitors financial flows. To manage the resources of the organization, the financial manager uses various tools of the financial mechanism. The key goals of enterprise financial management are to maximize profits, capitalization (market value) and solvency (liquidity) of the company in order to satisfy the interests of owners. The implementation of these goals is the responsibility of the head of the financial unit of the organization.

In addition, building the work of the financial service, selecting qualified specialists and monitoring the process and results of their activities, which are the key responsibilities of any manager. The implementation of the financial management system in the company, as a rule, is carried out by a special unit, which can be represented either by one employee or a full-fledged department. At the head of such a financial service is its own leader. Based on the size of the organizational structure and industry specifics of the enterprise, financial management functions can be distributed among several departments.

Theoretical aspects of research.

The theory of financial resources presented in works of foreign and Russian authors, for example, the implementation of the strategy of companies received a scientific theoretical analysis and widely presented in

works of such foreign authors as R. Holt, F. Cheng, J. Keynes, Y. Brikhem & Gapenski L., R. Kaplan & J. Hicks, as well as Russian and domestic, such as Homich I., A. Kovaleva, G. Polyak, D. Moliakov, Saffronov & Belolipetskii V. To the development problems of forming the general strategy of the organization contributed to the fundamental works of such foreign scientists as B. Karloff, G. KleinerM. Meskon & Ansoff I. Scientists such as V. Horn & A. Sheremet have dedicated their works to the basic research in the field of financial management. The work of the above scholars determined the theoretical basis for the study of financial activities of the corporate enterprises. These studies consider the selected issues of the financial management. In the economic domestic and foreign literature practically there are no works devoted to the systematic study of the problems of the strategy of financial resources management of corporate enterprises in modern conditions. The problem of strategy management of financial resources for corporate enterprises is not sufficiently investigated in the scientific literature from the point of view of its development and implementation in the modern financial situation[1].

Among the Uzbek scientists, such scientists have contributed to this direction: A.V.Vahobov, T.S.Malikov, A.T.Ibroximov, N.F.Ishonqulov R.X.Karlibaeva, M.Yu.Raximov, A.G.Ibragimov, Z.R.Madaminova, M.E.Raxmataliyev and etc.

Finance should be understood not only and not so much as money itself, financial means and financial resources. It is rather financial relations, as well as cash flows and cash funds generated in the process of these relations[2].

Fig. 1. Finance as an economic category[3]

Finances are monetary and economic relations that arise as a result of the movement of money and the financial flows generated in the process, which is closely interconnected with the financial funds of an economic entity created in the same period (Fig. 1).

Enterprise financial management, like any management system, includes an object and a subject, that is, a managed and managing subsystem (Fig. 2). The subject of management in the financial management system is primarily the organizational structure, as well as financial tools, information base and technical means

of financial management. The organizational structures of financial management of an enterprise can be designed in different ways, it depends on the size of the enterprise, form of ownership, specifics of activity, etc.[4]. In a small organization, all financial management functions can be performed either by the chief accountant (accountant) or the accountant together with the director. A large company is characterized by the allocation of special services (department of finance, financial department), which function directly with the accounting department.

Fig. 2. The structure of enterprise financial management systems[5]

Financial tools, or various techniques, methods, models, form the core of the science of financial management and will be discussed in detail in the following chapters of this tutorial. The financial management information base contains any information of a financial nature. This may include the financial statements of the enterprise, data from commodity, stock and currency exchanges, information from the banking sector, etc. The information base must also include legal information - laws, government decrees, statutory documents, regulations and instructions governing the work of a particular enterprise[5].

Technical financial management tools are modern means of computing and telecommunication technology that allow you to optimize the stages of collecting, transmitting and converting information as much as possible[6][7]. The object of management in the financial management system is financial relations that arise between participants in economic activity, as well as

various parts of the financial system, financial resources and their sources.

Methodological aspects of research.

The financial management process consists of several interrelated stages: planning of financial receipts, determination of sources of receipts, planning of directions of financial expenditures, receipt and expenditure of funds, formation of reserves. At the same time, different methods are used for planning and forecasting finances[8]. The main goals of the company are already laid down in the planning of finances. The plan contains both sources of income and directions for spending finance[9]. On the basis of which it is possible to assume the degree of investment activity of the enterprise. The choice of planning method depends on the style of management, factors affecting finances, the existing financial mechanism and the policy of the enterprise[10].

And also the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of financial management may look like this[11][12]:

1. Conversations are held with managers, interviews are taken from staff, documentation is collected and analyzed. The goal is to identify weaknesses in the financial management of the enterprise, to determine areas for improvement.

2. All loan documents are analyzed. The information base is: loan agreements, provisions on the accounting policy of the organization, all types of company reporting.

3. The financial policy of the company is controlled. The assessment begins with an analysis of the deviations of the company's actual performance from the planned ones. If the error is 5% or more, then the reasons are clarified and ways are considered how to prevent this from happening in the future.

Research and analyze of research.

According to the analysis, the financial management of the enterprise is carried out in the context of the following areas[6]:

- financial relations;
- policy in the field of issue of securities and payment of dividends;
- management of financial and real investments of the company.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of decisions made in these areas requires the development of an appropriate methodology, including the choice of objects and evaluation criteria, such as[2][13]:

1. Working capital and capital management. It includes the calculation and analysis of such indicators as the turnover ratio, load factor, capital productivity and capital intensity, return on capital and assets of the enterprise.

2. Financial risk management. It involves the use of various tools: diversification, insurance, risk hedging.

3. System of non-cash payments. There are analyzed the effectiveness and expediency of the applied forms of non-cash payments and estimated the speed of operations and the costs of their implementation.

4. System of business planning and budgetary funds. In this case, we study the degree of adaptation of the company to market conditions, the effectiveness of the organizational structure of the enterprise[14].

5. Management of the company's cash structure. The main goal is to minimize the cost of raising capital and maximize the market value of the company.

6. System for attracting investments. Priority is given to long-term investments. The presence of "long" money in the company reduces the risk of loss of liquidity and solvency.

7. The effectiveness of the organization and its business activity. The main indicators for analysis are the turnover periods of the company's accounts payable and receivable.

8. Dynamics and level of financial success of the company. The quantitative and qualitative indicators of the company's financial condition are assessed: different types of profit (EBIT, EBITDA, net, gross) and profitability (capital, production, sales).

Conclusion.

Thus, the financial resource management system is characterized by the interrelation and continuous interaction of two subsystems (object and subject). The purpose of this system is to provide optimal conditions

for the formation, use, optimization of financial resources in the course of economic activity. The formation of an effective system for managing financial resources will favor the restoration of their competitiveness, increase the well-being of owners, contribute to a faster renewal of fixed assets, and allow maintaining solvency and a proper level of profitability.

In addition, for the rational management of financial resources and the financial condition of an enterprise, it is necessary to analyze and control the process of formation, distribution and movement of financial flows, as well as their overall dynamics in absolute terms and compliance with regulatory indicators in relative terms.

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